

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers,

It is my pleasure to announce the forth regular issue of this year. Also this time, I'd like to gratefully thank all institutions and individuals - including the consortium members, editorial board members and the authors - for all the support and effort to make J.UCS one of the high quality journals in computer science. I'd also like to use this opportunity to point you to our closer integration of social media to be used to promote J.UCS and to spread the papers to a broader community and to share your favorite papers with your peers.

In this issue, I'd like to introduce five high quality papers on distinguished topics from computer science. A collaborative research form China and the US by Jian Fan, Yuliang Zheng, and Xiaohu Tang discusses the Signcryption approach, which is a public key cryptographic technique that is particularly suited for mobile communications. Tomasz A. Gorazd and Jacek Krzaczkowski from Poland show in their theoretical work that the term satisfiability problem for finite algebras is in NQL. Hamid Reza Mahrooghi and Rasool Jalili from Iran outline their research and findings of an algebraic theory of epistemic processes. The authors Jennifer Pérez, Isidro Ramos, Jose A. Carsí, and Cristóbal Costa-Soria from Spain focus on model-driven development of aspect-oriented software architectures by contributing on a methodology for code generation from models specifying functional and non-functional requirements. Howard Spoelstra, Peter van Rosmalen, Evert van de Vrie, Matija Obreza, and Peter Sloep from The Netherlands introduce their research and finding of team formation and project-based learning support service for social learning networks.

Enjoy reading!

Cordially,

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